

FINITE ELEMENT ANALYSIS OF THE IMPACT RESPONSE OF CFRP COMPOSITE PLATES

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ABSTRACT

The capability of a new constitutive model for composite materials, implemented in the nonlinear finite element code, LS-DYNA3D, is evaluated by carrying out a series of numerical simulations involving low velocity impact of laminated plates. The predictive capability of this model is assessed relative to that of the existing composite damage model in LS-DYNA3D by comparing the computed results from both models with impact test results. It is demonstrated that the new model, which is based on continuum damage mechanics, offers a more versatile and numerically robust tool for predicting the progression of damage in composite structures.

INTRODUCTION

Damage of composite structures due to impact events is perhaps one of the most important aspects of behaviour that inhibits widespread application of composite materials. An impact event can induce a substantial amount of damage in composites, the mode and extent of which are often difficult to predict. Understanding the deformation and failure mechanisms involved in the impact of composite targets is important in effectively designing a protection system to defeat a projectile. To achieve this design goal, it is necessary to have a reliable analysis tool that can deal with the intricate details of impact events.

Although different approaches for analysis of impact events are available, finite element analyses which are based on rigorous constitutive models provide the most detailed information on the spatial and temporal distribution of damage during impact. To this end, the transient nonlinear finite element code, LS-DYNA3D [1], has proven to be a powerful numerical tool. Currently, all composite material models in LS-DYNA3D assume that the response of an individual lamina is linear elastic (or nonlinear elastic in in-plane shear) up to failure. The various models differ, however, in their formulation of the failure criteria used to signal the onset of damage in a lamina. These criteria are either non-interactive, e.g. maximum stress criteria, or interactive, e.g. Hashin's [2] criteria which distinguish between fibre and matrix failure modes. All models assume that in the post-failure regime a lamina behaves in an ideally brittle manner with the dominant stiffness and stress components reduced to zero instantaneously. This assumption is clearly unrealistic as it disregards the constraints that are imposed on the failed lamina by the adjacent laminae and undamaged elements in the neighbourhood of the damage site. The net

result of these constraints is that, from a macroscopic viewpoint, the stress release and stiffness reductions occur gradually rather than abruptly. This behaviour can be incorporated in numerical analyses through a homogenized model which exhibits strain softening. One such model, based on the principles of continuum damage mechanics, has recently been developed by Matzenmiller, Lubliner and Taylor (MLT) [3] for the nonlinear analysis of composite materials. Because of its computationally-oriented nature and sound mechanics base, we have implemented the MLT model into LS-DYNA3D as a user material module for laminated shell elements.

The purpose of this paper is to demonstrate the capability of the MLT model in predicting the impact response of laminated plates using LS-DYNA3D. Through comparisons with available low velocity impact test results on CFRP plates [4, 5], the relative performances of an existing composite model [6] in LS-DYNA3D and the newly incorporated MLT model are assessed.

NUMERICAL MODEL

The finite element mesh adopted for this study (Fig. 1), represents a simplified model of the impact test setup [5]. The relatively high stiffness of the test apparatus (impactor and specimen support frame) compared to the transverse stiffness of the composite plate allowed the following two simplifying assumptions be made. First, the plate was considered to be simply-supported around the perimeter of the test frame opening (127 mm x 76.2 mm). Second, the steel impactor (25.4 mm in diameter) was treated as rigid and only the contact surface was discretized using rigid shell elements. Preliminary simulations, performed to examine the validity of these assumptions, indicated that the results from the simplified model compared closely with those obtained using a more sophisticated model which took into account the flexibility of the impactor and the supporting frame.

The plate was modelled using Belytschko-Lin-Tsay shell elements [7] with a single integration point in the plane of the element. A one point quadrature rule per lamina was used for through-thickness integration. The laminate lay-up was specified by assigning the lamina orthotropic material properties and fibre orientation angle to each through-thickness integration point. It is important to note that the use of shell elements did not allow for local indentation or delamination type failures. Contact between the impactor and plate was modelled using an intermittent contact algorithm based on the penalty stiffness approach.

CONSTITUTIVE MODEL

Two constitutive models were considered in this study. The first, developed by Chang and Chang [6], represents the more traditional ply discount method which has been used in numerical codes to model the progressive failure of laminated composites. The lamina is assumed to be linear elastic up to failure. After failure, a ply is assumed to lose its load carrying capacity in the dominant stress direction associated with the failure mode. The failure is assumed to be instantaneous and the elastic constants are reduced to zero in a predetermined number of time steps based on the dynamic stability of the model.

The second constitutive model adopted for this study was based on the elastic-brittle composite damage model by Matzenmiller *et al.* [3]. The premise of this model is that a unidirectional lamina can be represented as a homogenized continuum, irrespective of its damage state [8]. Damage is assumed to take the form of a distribution of disk like cracks oriented parallel or normal to the fibre direction. In this manner, symmetry of the lamina is preserved throughout the damage evolution. Three parameters, ω_{11} , ω_{22} and ω_{12} , are introduced as measures of damage leading to the plane stress compliance relationship:

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \varepsilon_{11} \\ \varepsilon_{22} \\ \gamma_{12} \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 1/(1-\omega_{11})E_1 & -\nu_{12}/E_1 & 0 \\ & 1/(1-\omega_{22})E_2 & 0 \\ \text{Sym} & & 1/(1-\omega_{12})G_{12} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \sigma_{11} \\ \sigma_{22} \\ \tau_{12} \end{Bmatrix} \quad (1)$$

where E_1, E_2, G_{12} and ν_{12} are the usual elasticity constants of the undamaged lamina. The prediction of failure is based on the concept of a threshold function, r , similar to the yield surface in plasticity theory. The elastic region is bounded by a series of surfaces $f(\sigma_{ij}, \omega_{ij}, r)$ associated with different lamina failure modes. In the present model, these failure surfaces are based on Hashin's lamina failure criteria [2].

Although it is useful to develop the constitutive model in stress space, the implementation of this model in an explicit numerical code generally requires a strain controlled approach. This has a secondary benefit if a strain softening response is to be incorporated, as in the current formulation. It is well understood that stress-strain relationships which incorporate a descending branch are stable only under strain controlled conditions.

In the derivation of the model, no mention is made of the physical characteristics of the damage variable. At present, only a general mathematical form of the damage variable is proposed:

$$\omega = 1 - e^{-(\varepsilon/\varepsilon_f)^m} \quad (2)$$

where ε_f is the nominal failure strain and m is a constant. Figure 2 shows the uniaxial stress-strain response according to the MLT model. Matzenmiller *et al.* noted that the function given in Eqn. (2), representing a Weibull distribution, can be derived from a statistical analysis of the probability of failure of a bundle of fibres with initial defects. The numerical formulation of the MLT model which was incorporated in LS-DYNA3D is based on a damage function of this form. A major difficulty arises in characterizing the descending or softening portion of the stress-strain curve, an extremely difficult test to perform.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Numerical simulations were carried out for a series of impact events with incident energy levels of 9.5, 22 and 33 J imparted on CFRP plates made of T800H/3900-2 fibre/resin system with a laminate stacking sequence of [45/0/-45/90]_{3S} and total thickness of 4.65 mm. Corresponding experimental results were obtained using drop-weight (high mass, low velocity) and gas-gun (low mass, high velocity) impact tests [4,5]. The lamina material properties used are listed in Table 1 [9].

Figure 3 compares the longitudinal stress-strain curves according to the Chang and Chang (CC) model and the MLT model for $m = 2$ and 10. As shown in the figure, these values of m represent two distinctly different responses, namely, a tough behaviour for $m = 2$ and a brittle behaviour for $m = 10$. The latter behaviour is very similar to the CC instantaneous unloading model up to the maximum stress level. Beyond this point, however, the MLT model with $m = 10$ exhibits a continuous strain softening response characteristic of quasi-brittle materials. The numerical simulations reported here use the three stress-strain models for comparative studies. Although the MLT model allows for different degrees of strain softening, characterized by the value of the constant m , in the longitudinal, transverse and in-plane shear loading modes, the same value of m was used for all three loading modes.

Figures 4 and 5 show a comparison between the measured contact force-time history and those predicted using the CC and MLT models for the 9.5 J and 22 J, low mass (314 g) impact events, respectively. For the 9.5 J event, the numerical predictions virtually overlap and reflect the observed undamaged plate response. For the 22 J event, the predictions deviate noticeably at about 0.4 ms after impact. This is indicative of the onset of failure. The MLT model with $m = 2$ yields results that simulate an elastic response with little or no damage. The CC model, on the other hand, predicts very sharp oscillations in the contact force after initial failure; a direct result of the abrupt unloading assumption in the model. Among the numerical results presented, the MLT model with $m = 10$ appears to yield a more realistic force-time profile.

Figure 6(a) shows a comparison of the force-time histories for the 33 J, low mass impact event. Clearly the MLT model with $m = 10$ results in a better prediction of the peak forces and shape of the force-time curve.

Figure 6(b) shows a comparison between the predicted time histories of the fibre strain at the back-face of the laminate (45° ply) in an element close to the midpoint of the plate. Since the instantaneous failure predicted by the CC model provides no energy absorption after failure the load is shed rapidly to the neighbouring plies. This leads to propagation of failure through the plate and is responsible for the large strains shown in Fig. 6(b). The significantly lower post-failure strains predicted by the MLT models are indicative of a more gradual decrease in the load carrying capability of a failed ply.

Figure 6(c) depicts the predicted state of fibre damage in the back-face at the conclusion of the impact event. Fibre failure is expected to be dominant on the back-face due to the global bending effects. For the MLT models, the fringe plots represent different degrees of damage marked by values of ω_{11} . For the CC model, the solid patches represent zones that have completely failed while the remaining zones are entirely elastic. The ability to display the level of damage in a spatially continuous fashion is an attractive feature of the MLT model. To aid in the interpretation of the fringe plots, it is useful to note that the critical values of the damage parameter ω_{11} at the peak stress ($\sigma_{11} = X_t$) are $\omega_{11}^* = 0.39$ (for $m = 2$) and $\omega_{11}^* = 0.09$ (for $m = 10$). It can be seen that for $m = 2$, the zones that have just failed (i.e. $\omega_{11} \geq \omega_{11}^*$) are localized in the central region of the plate. In other words, the overall behaviour is close to being elastic. The failed zones according to the CC model are spread over a long narrow strip, while the MLT model with $m = 10$ predicts a relatively smaller failure zone. Qualitatively, the latter prediction agrees well with the fibre breakage zone detected using deply techniques reported in [5].

Figures 7(a), 7(b) and 7(c) show the corresponding plots for the 33 J, high mass impact event. Again, the predictions of the MLT model with $m = 10$ compare remarkably well with the experimental data.

The numerical results presented indicate that the MLT model is a versatile constitutive model that has considerable potential for application to progressive damage modelling of composite structures. The model is limited at present by the lack of a standard testing procedure that can be used to characterize the strain softening behaviour. One practical option is to numerically calibrate the value of m that best represents the response for a specific impact test on a given laminate. This value may then be used in simulating the behaviour of the same laminate under different impact conditions.

CONCLUSIONS

The implementation of a new constitutive model, based on continuum damage mechanics, into the finite element code, LS-DYNA3D, proves to be promising as a numerical tool for simulation of progressive damage in laminated composite structures under impact loading. Despite the limitation in its physical characterization, the formulation presents a unique and interesting approach to the numerical simulation of damage in composite materials. The strain softening feature of the model provides new insight into energy absorption due to fracture and offers a more robust alternative to the available instantaneous failure models. To extend the effectiveness of this new model, standard test methods have to be devised to characterize the strain softening response of a given composite material. The present study represents the first step in an ongoing effort by the authors to develop a versatile and robust constitutive model for composite materials.

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Table 1: Lamina elastic and failure properties of T800H/3900-2.[9]

Elastic Parameters		Strength Parameters	
Longitudinal Modulus, E_1	152.4 GPa	Longitudinal Tensile, X_t	2089 MPa
Transverse Modulus, E_2	9.2 GPa	Longitudinal Compressive, X_c	1482 MPa
In-Plane Shear Modulus, G_{12}	4.3 GPa	Transverse Tensile, Y_t	79 MPa
Poisson's Ratio, ν_{12}	0.35	Transverse Compressive, Y_c	231 MPa
		In-Plane Shear, S	133 MPa

Figure 1: Exploded view of the FEM model.

Figure 2: Stress-strain behaviour according to the MLT model.

Figure 3: Comparison of stress-strain models (fibre direction).

Figure 4: Predicted and measured force-time history for an impact energy of 9.5 J ($v = 7.8$ m/s, $m = 314$ g)

Figure 5: Predicted and measured force-time history for an impact energy of 22 J ($v = 11.9$ m/s, $m = 314$ g)

Figure 6(a): Predicted and measured force-time history for an impact energy of 33 J ($v = 14.5$ m/s, $m = 314$ g)

Figure 6(b): Predicted back-face fibre strain close to the plate centre for an impact energy of 33 J ($v = 14.5$ m/s, $m = 314$ g)

Figure 6(c): Back-face fibre failure predicted using the CC model and corresponding back-face fibre damage (ω_{11}) predicted by the MLT model ($m = 2$ and $m = 10$) for an impact energy of 33 J ($v = 14.5$ m/s, $m = 314$ g). Note the fringe levels shown for both MLT predictions range from 0 (no damage) to ω^* (ω at $\sigma = X_t$).

Figure 7(a): Predicted and measured force-time history for an impact energy of 33 J ($v = 3.3$ m/s, $m = 6141$ g)

Figure 7(b): Predicted back-face fibre strain close to the plate centre for an impact energy of 33 J ($v = 3.3$ m/s, $m = 6141$ g)

Figure 7(c): Back-face fibre failure predicted using the CC model and corresponding back-face fibre damage (ω_{11}) predicted by the MLT model ($m = 2$ and $m = 10$) for an impact energy of 33 J ($v = 3.3$ m/s, $m = 6141$ g). Note the fringe levels shown for both MLT predictions range from 0 (no damage) to ω^* (ω at $\sigma = X_c$).